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КУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЯ

CULTURAL STUDIES

Синельщикова О.Д.

Продюсер, AN Media.

Тактические подходы к развитию российской киноиндустрии путем привлечения «runaway productions»*

Аннотация. В контексте процессов трансформации глобальной экономики и кризиса современной международной системы актуальность комплексной научной оценки состояния российской киноиндустрии отражает необходимость развития национального кино в России, как стране, обладающей богатыми и самобытными традициями в области искусства кино.

Очевидно, что производство кинофильмов мирового уровня требует постоянного развития интегрированной инфраструктуры, а также совместной материально-технической базы и наличия инвестиционных фондов для создания и реализации совместных кинопродуктов.

Также для развития киноиндустрии применяется метод, имеющий название «Сбежавшее производство». Этот термин используется американской голливудской индустрией для обозначения кино- и телепродукции, предназначенной для первоначального выпуска/выставки или телевизионной трансляции в США, но фактически снятой за пределами непосредственного района Лос-Анджелеса (включая Голливуд), будь то в другой стране, другом штате США или в другой части Калифорнии.

Цель статьи – охарактеризовать тактические подходы к развитию российской киноиндустрии путем привлечения «Runaway productions».

Практическая значимость исследования заключается в том, что разработка подходов к развитию российской киноиндустрии может повлиять на повышение ее эффективности и конкурентоспособности.

Ключевые слова: российская киноиндустрия, тактические подходы, пути привлечения, «Runaway productions».

Sinelshchikova O.D.

Producer, AN Media.

Tactical approaches to the development of the Russian film industry through the involvement of runaway productions

Abstract. In the context of the processes of global economic transformation and the crisis of the modern international system, the relevance of a comprehensive scientific assessment of the state of the Russian film industry reflects the need to develop national cinema in Russia, as a country with rich and distinctive traditions in the art of cinema.

It is obvious that the production of world-class films requires the continuous development of an integrated infrastructure, as well as a joint material and technical base and the availability of investment funds for the creation and realization of joint film productions.

A method called «runaway production» is also used to develop the film industry. This term is used by the U.S. Hollywood industry to refer to film and television productions intended for initial

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release/exhibition or television broadcast in the United States, but actually filmed outside the immediate Los Angeles area (including Hollywood), whether in another country, another U.S. state, or another part of California.

The purpose of the article is to characterize tactical approaches to the development of the Russian film industry through the involvement of Runaway productions.

The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that the development of approaches to the development of the Russian film industry can affect the improvement of its efficiency and competitiveness.

Key words: Russian film industry, tactical approaches, ways to attract Runaway productions.

Introduction

The problem of the crisis in the film industry has taken on a global scale and has affected not only the interests of filmmakers, but all audiences without exception. As a result, there is a need to develop a common strategy related to the achievement of competitive advantages by Russian film companies in the context of globalization [1].

The development of Russian cinema as part of the global film business can proceed according to various scenarios, including the involvement of «Runaway productions».

Materials and methods of research

The development of the Russian film industry and ways of its development are investigated in the article with the use of methods: study of theoretical aspects of the topic, discourse analysis, analysis of practical directions of the film industry development, including through the involvement of «Runaway productions».

Results and discussion

The processes of market globalization, developing against the backdrop of intensive scientific and technological progress, have led to the production of film products that are universal in nature, becoming more highly technological but less diverse [2].

Appearing at all stages of the film process, globalization has the following most significant aspects of influence on the film industry (figure 1).

Investment globalization relates to the involvement of entrepreneurs in film production and reflects the increasing number of film producers around the world.

The globalization of film consumption is mainly related to changing patterns of audience interest, shaped by global consumer preferences for films aimed, for example, at children or comic book fans.

Globalization of production is manifested in expensive and innovative film projects created with the participation of business structures from different countries [3].

Figure 1. Aspects of globalization affecting the film industry.

The globalization of the organization of film production involves the development of global organizational and legal forms of film business, and the widespread use of transnational corporations.

Russian cinema has been going through a difficult time in recent years. For example, during the pandemic, cinemas were closed or operated with restrictions, resulting in huge financial losses. Later, as of March 2022, many major Western film companies announced their withdrawal from the Russian market. Universal Pictures, Walt Disney Pictures, Warner Bros., Sony Pictures, and Paramount Pictures, the major film giants of Hollywood, no longer show their films in Russia [4].

Below is an analysis of the box office receipts of Russian cinemas over the past few years (figure 2).

In 2021, before the departure of foreign companies, box office collections amounted to 40.7 billion rubles, which was 78% higher compared to 2020. Box office collections in 2021 gradually returned to pre-pandemic values, but did not reach them yet. They were 26% lower compared to the 2019 figure. It is worth noting that

Figure 2. Dynamics of cash collections, bln. rub.

the share of Russian-made films in box office receipts amounted to only 25.5%.

In 2022, after the withdrawal of foreign companies, the share of Russian movies naturally increased. There was an increase

Figure 3. Russian cinema films.

the decline continued: collections - 3.3 billion rubles, viewers - 13 million. But in the summer of 2023, the trend changed slightly: the collections increased to 5.6 billion rubles, and the number of viewers - almost 20 million [7].

There is also the problem of increasing the budget of films. For example, the budget of Russian films has recently increased on average from 40% to 70%, depending on the script. Whereas two years ago the production cost of films ranged from 50 million to 70 million rubles, today 70 million is already the minimum for such a project. The upper limit, in turn, can now reach 120 million. Obviously, the growth of costs in the spectacular cinema segment, where production is much more technically complex, will be even higher.

«Runaway productions» can help solve some of the problems of Russian cinema (figure 5).

Thus, there are many advantages to shooting films abroad, one of them being the opportunity to significantly reduce production costs. Foreign subsidies provided to film companies are one of the key factors in reducing the cost of producing a movie. Because of this, the budget of the movie is slightly reduced, allowing the money to be saved and invested in other aspects of production.

The Runaway productions approach is one solution that can alleviate some of the financial problems facing the Russian film industry. This term describes shooting movies in locations with more favorable conditions for production, helping to save on costs and ensure a high quality picture. This practice can not only reduce costs, but also open up new opportunities for filmmakers and screenwriters to find interesting locations and unusual settings for their projects [8].

In addition, coproduction and international distribution of films shot abroad can significantly increase their budgets. For example, films coproduced from different countries usually have a greater chance of successful worldwide distribution. This opens up new opportunities for international audiences, increasing the potential profits and popularity of the movie.

Consequently, choosing a location for filming a movie is an important strategic step that can determine the success of the project and its financial efficiency. A suitable strategy of cooperation with foreign partners can be the key to budget growth and commercial success of the film.

This approach also contributes to the development of the local film and television industry, as local crews, actors, managers and assistant directors gain valuable

Figure 5. Problems solved with Runaway productions.

experience and become more attractive to other producers [9].

Conclusions

At present, the Russian film industry is faced with the fact that creating high-quality content requires not only talent, but also careful training of specialists. There is a problem of a shortage of personnel in Russia, primarily qualified scriptwriters, technical specialists and directors.

A serious obstacle stands in the way of creating a new generation of outstanding specialists. It takes not only time for training and education, but also a huge effort on the part of educational institutions to produce new quality cinema.

Script writing, filming, post-production - all these stages require time and careful approach [10].

The art of cinema has always been one of the most sought-after arts, attracting the attention of a wide audience. Nevertheless, one of the serious problems faced by movie makers is the constant increase in budgets. This applies not only to Hollywood pictures, but also to domestic cinematography. Recently, the budgets of Russian films have increased by 40-70%, depending on the complexity of the script and requirements.

Thus, «Runaway productions» represent an important tool to promote the development of Russian cinematography and increase the competitiveness of its products on the world stage. The introduction of this practice may become the key to creating more high-quality and interesting films that attract the attention of audiences and contribute to the flourishing of the Russian film industry [11].

Список литературы / References

[1] Kolobova E. Yu. Formation of the competitiveness management system of economic entities of film exhibition // St. Petersburg Economic Journal. 2017. № 2. P. 155-164.

- [2] Ogurchikova P.K. Mastery of the producer of cinema and television / P.K. Ogurchikova, V.V. Padeisky, V.I. Sidorenko – Moscow: UNITIDANA, 2018. 863 p.
- [3] Novikova A.A. A. Hybridity as a defining feature of the television format // Bulletin of Moscow University. Journalism. 2020. № 10. P. 53-58.
- [4] Ten main results of 2023 for film distribution. Trends whose impact on the industry can be assessed as early as this year // Film Distribution Bulletin. 2024. № 50 // URL: http://www.kinometro.ru/analytics/show/name/10_summary_ru_boxoffice_9884.
- [5] Problems of modern cinema // URL: <https://technopolis.susu.ru/en/component/k2/4273/проблемы-современного-кинематографа>.
- [6] Federal Fund for Social and Economic Support of National Cinematography // URL: <http://www.fondkino.ru>.
- [7] Film Industry of Russia // URL: <https://dcenter.hse.ru/data/2017/09/15/1173122290/Киноиндустрия%20России%202024.pdf>.
- [8] Diorio, L. 'Politicians focus on runaway production.' Hollywood Reporter, 25 June 2017.
- [9] Ulich, Pamela Conley, Simmons, Lance. 'Film Production: To Run or Stay Made in the USA.' Loyola of Los Angeles Entertainment Law Review, 2018. Vol. 21. P. 357.
- [10] Freeman, Gregory, Kaiser, Jack, Sidhu, Nancy, Huang, George, Montoya, Michael. What is the cost of runaway manufacturing? Jobs, wages, economic output and state tax revenues are at risk when film production leaves California. Los Angeles: Los Angeles County Economic Development Corporation, August 2015.
- [11] Centre for Entertainment Research and Data. The Migration of Feature Film Production from the United States to Canada and Beyond, Production Report 2021. Los Angeles, 2022.